

NURSES' KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE REGARDING TRIAGE MANAGEMENT IN EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS, PESHAWAR, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Triage has been used in emergency departments for prioritizing patients to determine which patients require immediate treatment according to their emergent health condition. Triage nurse is typically the first person on emergency when the patient is presented in emergency department. . According to previous studies, there is a lack of significant evidence to support the reliability and the predictability of the practices of nurses to be measured. **Objective:** To assess the triage knowledge and practice of registered nurses working in the emergency department of tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted in five tertiary care hospitals of KPK. Using a convenient sampling technique, 120 nurses were included in the study. Data was collected using a valid and reliable tool that was adopted and modified. The registered nurses who were present at the time of data collection were included, while managerial nurses were excluded. Data was analyzed through SPSS version 22. **Results:** The study revealed that 60% of the participants had good triage knowledge, and in terms of practice, 75% had good triage practice. Chi-square test was applied to find any significant association between the demographic variable and knowledge and practice. Age ($P < 0.001$) has a significant association with knowledge, and there is no significant association between the triage knowledge and practice ($p > 0.08$). **Conclusions:** The study revealed a good level of triage knowledge and practice of nurses and recommends adding emergency triage teaching sessions, involving a part of nurses and student nurses, to address the knowledge deficit areas, hence improving practice.

INTRODUCTION

Triage is the process of determining which patients receive priority treatment based on the correct identification of their severity of illness or injury (1). With more patients visiting emergency departments, authorities recognized a need to

determine which patients require immediate treatment (2). Triage is one of the most crucial and organized concepts for making decisions in emergency departments (3). A triage nurse is typically the first person on the emergency

counter when a patient is presented in the emergency department (4). The triage is classified into three distinct types, including military, disaster, and emergency triage (5). The triage system is introduced worldwide to lower the rate of mortality and help in sorting the patients in the emergency department, which in turn reduces the waiting time of the patients for receiving treatment (2). In the last century, triage has been used in emergency departments to prioritize patients according to their condition. The patients are prioritized as follows: the priority was given to patients with potentially life-threatening conditions, or limb-threatening conditions are considered as emergent, the second priority was given to patients with less or possibly serious as urgent cases, the third priority and lastly, the non-urgent cases who can be delayed up to several hours, as these patients may need bandages and aseptic techniques. The patient, as the fourth priority, is non-urgent and can be delayed (2). According to previous studies, there is a lack of significant evidence to support the reliability and predictability of the practice of nurses to be measured (6). Many factors can contribute to improper decision making in emergency departments by nurses, including overflow of the patients, anxiety level of the patients and their family members; influence on the patient care and decision making (3).

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non-urgent and can be delayed (2). According to previous studies, there is a lack of significant evidence to support the reliability and the predictability of the practices of nurses to be measured (6). Many factors can contribute to improper decision-making in emergency departments by nurses, including overflow of patients, anxiety level of the patients, and their family members. These factors can have an enormous influence on patient care and decision-making (3).

Literature Review

Around 50% to 80% of people come to the emergency department for non-urgent reasons, which increases the cost as well as multiple consequences (7). Lack of expert staff can lead to economic crisis (8). According to a North Khuzestan study on the level of knowledge and performance of North Khuzestan medical emergency 115 personnel on pre-hospital triage, it is found that nurses have a low level of knowledge regarding triage. Related results have been reported of less triage knowledge (8). Education is essential for enhancing emergency departments (1). A systematic review of the knowledge level of nurses about hospital triage concludes that the knowledge level of nurses ranges from low to moderate (9). Children compose approximately 20% of overall emergency department visits and are at risk of being triaged properly because it is difficult to collect subjective data where complaints include some of the existing medical conditions and some new pediatric symptoms. The study claims the level of nurses' knowledge and attitude toward triage was improved post triage education as compared to pre triage education (10). The study of the nurses in Iran showed that triage nurses are at a moderate level of clinical practice and need effective plans to improve their professional capability (2). Another study in Ethiopia concluded that triage knowledge was at a low level as compared to skills and practice, which was good, where associations were between work experience and educational level (11).

Training should be provided to all nurses by the government or by medical departments, and

training sessions should be conducted to improve nurses' knowledge and practice. As observed from the above and previous studies, it is observed that nurses have low or moderate triage knowledge, but not enough to reduce the mortality rate by proper decision making and proper patient identification. Emergency nurses should know proper guidelines for patient safety and better results. A significant difference was found between the Nurses who had received triage education and training, according to the top academic journal in 2023.

Aims and objectives.

To assess the triage knowledge of registered nurses working in the emergency department of tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan.

To assess the triage practices of registered nurses working in the emergency department of tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan.

Significance of the Study

This study aims to provide insight into the level of knowledge and practice among nurses working in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. The findings will highlight areas for improvement and will be utilized in developing strategies or training sessions for enhancing triage knowledge and practice among nurses, contributing to improved health care.

Operational definitions

The following are the operational definitions used in the study.

Nurses' knowledge

The level of understanding by a knowledge questionnaire and the information that nurses possess about triage management, including principles, procedures, and protocols. Assessment of knowledge will be done by 1 to 18 items, and below 10 is considered poor knowledge, and above 10 is considered good knowledge.

Nurses practice.

The actual application of triage management skills by nurses in the emergency department, including decision making, patient prioritization, and adherence to protocol. The assessment of

practice will be determined by a questionnaire consisting of 1 to 13 questions. Below 7 is considered poor practice, and above 7 is considered good practice.

Methodology

The following outlines the research methodology employed in this study.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted among registered nurses at five major tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan, over a period of 3 months.

Study Setting:

The study has been conducted at the following hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan, which include two private sector hospitals and three public sector hospitals:

1. Rehman Medical Institute, Peshawar, Pakistan.
2. North-West General Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan.
3. Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar, Pakistan.
4. Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan.
5. Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, Pakistan.

Population:

Registered nurses working in the emergency department of tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan.

Sampling technique:

Convenient sampling techniques have been used for the selection of study participants.

Sample Size

For this study, a population of 120 is taken, a 5% margin of error, and a 95% confidence interval.

Inclusion Criteria

Registered nurses who are present at the time of data collection and are willing to participate.

Exclusion Criteria

Registered nurses who are in managerial positions and head nurses.

Data Collection Process & Tool:

A questionnaire developed by Phukubye et al. (2019) has been used to assess triage knowledge and practice among nurses, where Cronbach's alpha value for triage knowledge was 0.88, and Cronbach's alpha value for triage and 0.74 triage practice (12). The questionnaire was distributed to the willing participants with written informed consent before data collection. This questionnaire consists of 18 questions for triage knowledge and 13 questions for triage practice, which should be answered with either agree or disagree. To those with the correct answer, a score of 1 is given, and to those with incorrect answers, a score of 0 is given; a greater score indicates better triage knowledge and practice. In addition, the questions added in the sociodemographic data and taken as a variable for assessment are their gender, years of experience, prior triage knowledge, and prior triage training.

Data Analysis procedure

Data was analyzed through SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Descriptive statistics were analyzed for the data. Percentages and proportions were calculated for the qualitative variables, and means and standard deviations were calculated for the quantitative variables.

Results

A total of 120 nurses working in the emergency department participated in the study. A greater number of people, with 78.33% as shown in Table 1, had received the prior triage training, among them 49 were male and 71 were female, indicating a high number of females. The maximum year of experience of the nurses who participated in the study is 1 to 5 years. 49.17% of nurses received emergency training certificates, as shown in the table. The highest age group of participants was between 20 to 30, with a mean score of 28.83(±4.060) as shown in Table 2, Figure 1.

Table 1: sociodemographic characteristics of the participants

Variables		Frequency	Percentages
Gender	Female	71	59.17%
	Male	49	40.83%
Prior triage Training	Yes	94	78.33%
	No	26	21.67%
Additional emergency nursing trainings	In- service triage	31	25.83%
	Emergency nursing certificates	59	49.17%
	Others	30	25%

Table 2: Age of the participants

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation
Age	28.03	4.06

(Figure 1: Age of the participants)

Normality of data:

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were applied to check the normality of the data. As the data was not normally distributed (0.04), the median was calculated.

Knowledge of the participants regarding triage:

The overall knowledge score of the participants was categorized as 1 to 9, being poor knowledge, and 10 and > 10 being good knowledge, as shown in Figure 2.

(Figure 2: Triage knowledge of the participants)

Triage knowledge:

The overall mean score of triage knowledge is 10.0917 (1.78225) as shown in Table 1, and the total percentage is shown in Figure 5. The highest agreement of the participants is with the item triage, which is the sorting of patients into priority of illness and injury (freq = 111, 92.5%). Item 5 has a very low agreement with the participants, as a very small number of emergency

department nurses agreed with the statement that if an emergency sign is identified first, the patient's vital signs are assessed first (freq= 18, 15.0%), correct answers, and (freq= 102, 85.0%) incorrect answers. The second least scored question is item 10. (76.7%) of nurses gave the wrong response, where P indicates the pain, not the pulse.

Table 3: Questionnaire regarding triage knowledge

S. No	STATEMENTS	CORRECT		INCORRECT	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	Triage is the sorting of patients into priority of injuries or illnesses.	111	92.5	9	7.5
2.	The purpose of triage is to prevent deterioration or death of a patient while waiting in the queue for their turn.	27	22.5	93	77.5
3.	Triage Early Warning Signs are short- Triage Early Warning Signs.	67	55.8	53	44.2
4.	There are two Canadian Triage & Acuity Scale charts, one for children and adults.	99	82.5	21	17.5
5.	If an emergency sign is identified in the first step, the patient's vital signs first.	18	15.0	102	85.0
6.	If no emergency signs are identified in step 1, but an urgent sign is identified in step 2, the patient is Immediately triaged yellow and asked to wait.	79	65.8	41	34.2
7.	The Canadian Triage & Acuity Scale priority level yellow should be referred to the designated area for non-urgent.	42	35.0	78	65.0
8.	Patients triaged color WHITE should wait for 10 minutes before being attended.	39	32.5	81	67.5
9.	Nursing auxiliaries are not allowed to triage.	64	53.3	56	46.7
10.	AVPU is short for Alert, Verbal, Pulse, Unresponsive.	28	23.3	92	76.7
11.	Adult Triage Early Warning Score consists of the following parameters: Mobility, Respiratory rate, Heart rate, Diastolic blood pressure, Temperature, and AVPU.	99	82.5	21	17.5
12.	A tiny baby under two months should always be referred to the senior health care practitioner Once they have been comprehensively triaged.	110	91.7	10	8.3
13.	Patients with color green or (Priority 4) should be attended first when triaging.	52	43.3	68	56.7
14.	The Canadian Triage & Acuity Scale has 5 color coding or priorities.	104	86.7	16	13.3

15.	Triage is difficult and costly to implement in district emergency units.	88	73.3	32	26.7
16.	Patients with high social status, e.g., town mayor, school principals, politicians, etc., should be treated as very urgent even if triaged as color green.	62	51.7	68	48.3
17.	The discriminator list is not important for triage purposes.	55	45.8	64	53.3
18.	Triage knowledge is not important.	67	55.8	53	44.2

Practice of the participants regarding triage:

The overall practice score of the participants was categorized as from 1 to 6 as poor practice and >7 as good practice, as shown in Figure 3.

(Figure 3: triage practice of the participants)

The overall mean score of practice was 7.4750 (SD=1.69012), and the total percentage of practice is shown in Figure 6. The participants either agreed or disagreed with each statement. Item 10 states that the delays in waiting time can negatively impact the outcome of the patient's

condition, has the highest correct answers (freq=103, 85.5%), and the highest incorrect answers are for statement 3, which states that allocating the triage code is the last step in the triage process (freq=85, 70.8%).

Table 4: questionnaire regarding triage practice

STATEMENT		CORRECT		INCORRECT	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	The triage process should be practiced by professional nurses only	85	70.8	35	29.2
2.	The practice of triage starts with taking of vital signs of the patient.	100	83.3	20	16.7
3.	Allocating a triage code is the last step in the triage process.	35	29.2	85	70.8
4.	Calculation of Triage Early Warning Signs is done after allocating a triage code.	42	35.0	78	65.0
5.	Comparing the discriminator list and the Triage Early Warning Signs score is done before allocating a triage code.	87	72.5	33	27.5
6.	Triage reduces the waiting time of patients in emergency units.	86	71.7	34	28.3
7.	Waiting time should not be considered when rendering emergency care.	41	34.2	79	65.8
8.	Patients triaged as Yellow should wait for 10 minutes to be seen.	44	36.7	76	63.3
9.	Patients triaged as Green should wait for 1 h or less.	38	31.7	82	68.3
10.	Delays in waiting time can negatively impact the outcome of the patient's condition.	103	85.8	17	14.2
11.	Waiting time can never be improved in rural hospitals due to a shortage of human resources.	43	35.8	77	64.2
12.	Short waiting time in emergency units reduces overcrowding, and the result is patient satisfaction.	94	78.3	25	20.8
13.	It is illegal to delay triage in patients within emergency units	88	73.3	32	26.7

Relationship between triage knowledge and practice

There was no association ($p = > 0.08$) between triage knowledge and practice. The only association is with age ($P < 0.001$) of the participants; an increase in age shows an increase in the knowledge of the participants.

Discussions

The findings of a study done in Ethiopia and Iraq revealed that more than half of the nurses showed a moderate level of professional competence, clinical competence in terms of professional knowledge and practical skill (13) (14). To increase the effectiveness of emergency services and the quality of patient triage, nursing

managers should take the appropriate steps to improve these areas (2). It was discovered that providing triage nurses with training courses improved their clinical expertise and professional knowledge while also raising patient satisfaction with the standard of emergency care services.

A significant component of the current study was the assessment of the clinical judgment abilities of the triage nurses as a crucial component of clinical competency. In contrast with earlier research, the current study regarded clinical judgment as a crucial aspect of clinical competence because, as per Kantar and Alexander's (2012) study, clinical judgment is a critical competency for all nurses, particularly emergency nurses, and is crucial for accurately

identifying patients' issues and making clinical decisions. To enhance the clinical judgment skills of triage nurses, nursing managers must focus especially on this area in addition to professional knowledge and clinical expertise.

A similar study conducted in Saudi Arabia showed relatable results; the study reported that emergency department nurses showed very good and high levels of triage knowledge and practice (12). However, contrastingly, there was an association shown between knowledge and practice; as per this study, there is no such association found in the triage knowledge and practice. Moreover, a study conducted in Hawassa to assess the knowledge and skills of nurses showed a low triage knowledge score with (± 2.317) and a good skills level (11).

Limitations and strengths

This was a self-report-based study, and no observational study was done to assess the actual practice being done by nurses.

A study has been conducted in 3 major government and 2 private sectors of Peshawar, where nursing staff receive a high number of patients daily, which, however, gives a result that they go through good nursing triage practice and have been triaged well.

Recommendations

Further research can be done to assess the ratio of correct sorting of patients in organization, and as well as the organization can also take help from the recorded data to assess patients satisfaction and outcomes, which will help where to improve the skills and practice by enhancing the knowledge of nurses and to set new goals as well as nurses need to memorize the triage codes and the organization needs to hold sessions on the triage management, add them to their course curriculum for future benefit of nurses.

Conclusions

As the study has been conducted in the tertiary care hospitals where many patients visit daily with high patient inflow, it is very tricky to manage and triage them. This needs skilled and efficient nurses with good knowledge and practice for

better and accurate outcomes. The overall study revealed a good triage knowledge of 60% and good triage practice 75%. However, there is a notable gap of 40% poor knowledge of the participants, for which there should be sessions, seminars, and teaching plans for nurses to improve their knowledge for a better outcome, improve patients' safety, and build a good triage foundation. Practice is good for nurses compared to their knowledge of nurses.

Interestingly, no association was found between knowledge and practice with demographic data, except age with knowledge, nor knowledge and practice themselves have an association, which suggests that good or bad knowledge does not stem from good or bad practice. Good institutional protocols, proper planning, identifying and emphasizing nurses' goals and roles can also result in better and accurate results. Addressing and enhancing evidence-based practices can build a foundation for helping nurses to manage high-flow patient care. The study concluded level of nurses' knowledge and practice is at a good level in KPK.

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Ethical Consideration

This study received ethical approval from the Rehman College of Nursing and the respective hospitals. Participants have been informed about the study before participating and filled out the questionnaire after signing the informed consent. Participants' privacy is maintained and kept

confidential, and they also have the right to quit at any time during data collection if they do not want to complete the process of the study.

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